

Concept 6 – Connection to Sustainability

Part of the AquaVitae MOOC reading material

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Oysters are ecosystem engineers (sensu Jones et al. 1994) with many ecological functions. They contribute with both allogenic and autogenic engineering properties (Jones et al. 1994). As autogenic engineers, they generate shell structures that constitute an abiotic resource that support other species, e.g. interstitial-shell spaces that can be used as shelter from predators, colonization substrate for algae and invertebrates and refuge and foraging substrate for many invertebrates and fish (Arve 1960, Newell 1988, Lenihan 1999, Ozbay et al. 2017). Consequently, one of the great benefits of oyster farming is the development of an entire ecosystem around the culture structures and the oysters, which can be seen as temporary artificial bivalve reefs. The biodiversity values of these structures are well documented (Theuerkauf et al. 2021, The Nature Conservancy 2021) and can be exemplified by reports from fishermen from Santa Catarina Island (Brazil) who describe that, “around oyster lanterns, it is an excellent place to fish due to the presence of fish that had previously disappeared due to overfishing”. In fact, it is recorded that oyster aquaculture increases biodiversity by 1.3 times and abundance of associated organisms by 1.7 times (The Nature Conservancy 2021, Figure 1).

Figure 1. Impact of oyster aquaculture (among other activities and bivalves species) on species abundance and diversity in comparison to reference sites. Figure from the Nature Conservancy¹

¹ <https://www.globalseafood.org/advocate/tnc-restorative-aquaculture-can-improve-marine-habitats-biodiversity/>

Other services provided by the autogenic properties of oyster culture are wave attenuation and that the oyster culture can act as barriers for storms and tides, hence increasing sediment stability and preventing sediment and shoreline erosion. The use of artificial oyster reefs to protect and control coastal erosion is already practiced in several countries, e.g. in the Netherlands and the United States (Alabama, Florida, Louisiana, Mississippi and Texas, Ysebaert et al. 2019). These effects are, however, poorly documented in oyster aquaculture to date (Gentry et al. 2020).

As allogenic engineers, oysters support water quality, eutrophication remediation, nutrient recapture and support benthic-pelagic coupling. As filter feeding organisms the oysters will clear the water from phytoplankton and suspended organic particles and deposit some of the material on the bottom in the form of pseudofeces (FOSTER-SMITH, 1975). The volume of filtered water or will vary with species, animal size, water temperature, water salinity and seston concentration (Ehrich and Harris 2015), but can reach approximately 5 L/hour for a large oyster, and consequently, oyster farming can have significant effects on water quality and clarity in an area. Improved water quality and clarity provides direct benefits to nearby habitats, e.g. seagrass meadows, which in turn are important as nursery areas and for carbon sequestration (Cloern 1982, Cerrato et al. 2004, Newell 2004, Wall et al. 2008, Sousa et al. 2009, Cerco & Noel 2010).

Feces and pseudofaeces (biodeposits) produced by bivalves also play a key role in the ecosystems but can both be a resource and a liability. A part of the feces and pseudofeces will remain in suspension and will be decomposed by bacteria, but the majority will be deposited on the sediment where it is ingested by infauna and deposit feeders and decomposed by bacteria. The process of decomposition of biodeposits by bacteria and subsequent release of nutrients is referred to as remineralization. The deposits modify the sediment by adding high loads of organic-enriched particles, thus affecting the organic matter content and oxygen conditions of the sediment (Castel et al. 1989, Commito et al. 2008) and hence the infauna community (Castel et al. 1989, Dittmann 1990). Under the right circumstances this may be beneficial and may enhance the infauna (Kochmann et al. 2008, Markert et al. 2010), but if the volumes of biodeposits are too high, e.g. in areas with high concentration of particulate matter, low water circulation and high stocking density of shellfish, negative effects in terms of reduced species richness and abundance of infauna can occur (Castel et al. 1989, Dittmann 1990). In this perspective, however, it is important to highlight that oyster culture self-regulates, and as an environmental imbalance occurs, it will be manifested in the zootechnical performance of the oyster production, especially by reducing growth rates and reproduction.

The eutrophication remediation service provided by oyster has an important role in coastal waters. Currently, it is estimated that 60% of the coastal areas suffer from eutrophication (Theuerkauf et al. 2019). The potential of bivalves to mitigate eutrophication has been studied using different species in different regions (Jones and Preston 1999, Songsanngindra et al. 2000, Gifford et al. 2004, Nelson et al. 2004, Newell et al. 2005, Higgins et al. 2011). An example of application of bioremediation with bivalves is the Billion Oyster Project (BOP; <https://www.billionoysterproject.org>) developed by the Harbor School of New York, with significant positive effects in the New York area. As in New York harbor, polluted coastal environments are not suitable for food production as not only phytoplankton and suspended organic materials, but also pollutants, faecal pathogens and heavy metals can be bioaccumulated

in the oysters (O'Connor and Gifford, 2008). In such situations can oysters be farmed for other provisioning services, e.g. pearl production by pearl oyster, and environmental benefits could still be achieved at the same time as the oysters provide an excellent alternative for income. As with many ecosystem services, however, a balance between the service and the environment must be maintained. It is for example essential to know an area's ecological carrying capacity, i.e. in this case how much oyster aquaculture an area can sustain without depleting the food resources (phytoplankton, Ford 2011) so that negative interactions in terms of food competition between farmed and wild populations are avoided. This is also essential for the production of oysters in culture, as overstocking will result in low growth rates, prolonged production times and poor product quality.

Moreover, the uptake and incorporation of nutrients into oyster tissue has implications for the biogeochemical cycles of nitrogen and in particular, phosphorus. While nitrogen can be fixed and transferred from air to the sea by cyanobacteria, phosphorus is a limited substance whose biogeochemical process spans thousands of years. Currently, phosphorus is mined from mountains, and projections state that given the current use, the phosphorus reserves will be depleted in approximately 50 years (Cordel et al. 2009, Sverdrup et al. 2013). This is often referred to as “the phosphorus crisis” as 80% of the phosphorus is used in agriculture (Achary et al. 2017), and then transported with runoff and nutrient leakage to the sea which acts as a phosphorus sink. Bivalve culture in general, however, has the potential to act as a link between the sea and land, and contribute to loop closure by bringing nutrients back from the sea to different uses on land (Thomas et al. 2021, Sinah et al. 2022).

In terms of services relating to oyster aquaculture, the concept of restorative aquaculture (The Nature Conservancy, 2021) must be mentioned. The definition of restorative aquaculture is “Restorative aquaculture occurs when commercial or subsistence aquaculture provides direct ecological benefits to the environment, with the potential to generate net positive environmental outcomes.” (The Nature Conservancy, 2021). This can include eg. production of oyster seed or broodstock for restoration purposes (zu Ermgassen et al. 2020), natural spatfall from ongoing production when the oysters reproduce during the culture cycle (Delago 2021), and many of the services discussed above.

Oyster aquaculture is a high-quality food production system with a relatively low cradle-to-gate carbon footprint. The carbon dioxide (CO₂) and other greenhouse gasses released during operations (fuel, consumables, etc.) associated to the culture method (suspended or intertidal) and the biological production of CO₂ during shell formation (calcification, $2 \text{HCO}_3^- + \text{Ca}^{2+} \rightarrow \text{CaCO}_3 + \text{CO}_2 + \text{H}_2\text{O}$) and respiration ($\text{CH}_2\text{O} + \text{O}_2 \rightarrow \text{CO}_2 + \text{H}_2\text{O}$) processes contribute to this carbon footprint. Conversely, long-term burial of a portion of oyster faeces in the sediment contributes to carbon sequestration. The highest CF of oyster aquaculture is, however, from the culture operations, which is approximately one order of magnitude higher than the biological carbon footprint, and vary with culture technique. Consequently, improvements in production practices, infrastructure and logistics may reduce the climate impact of oyster production. Overall, the CF of oyster aquaculture is currently in the order of poultry or pig meat production.

As apparent, the effects, both positive and negative, of oyster culture are context dependent (see Theuerkauf et al. 2021, Figure 2). Ecological impacts of oyster culture is discussed above, yet other sustainability aspects also impact the general performance of oysters culture e.g as

discussed in concept 5 related to nutritional value and food safety, and in relation to concept 4 (grow out) as oyster culture systems (infrastructure) can affect social license of oyster aquaculture as the systems may be regarded as visual pollution of otherwise pristine marine areas. In contrast, oyster aquaculture can also be connected to eco-tourism or gastronomic tourism, e.g. oyster safari tours or restaurants which are closely linked to the production of oysters. Consequently, the socio-economic values of the environmental benefits provided by oyster aquaculture are widely recognized, particularly in terms of provisioning services (i.e. food production), improvement of local fishermen communities and quality of life, and a source of work and income for coastal communities, yet these effects are often not quantified.

In conclusion, oyster aquaculture has many advantages and supports a range of ecosystem services. It must, however, be mentioned that as for all food production, some disservices may also appear. Given proper site selection and production management, these can, to a large extent, be minimized, and in general the benefits of production outweighs the negatives, especially in comparison to terrestrial food production systems.

Figure 2. Aspects affecting the environmental impact of oyster aquaculture. Figure from Theuerkauf et al. (2021).

References

- Achary et al. (2017). Phosphite: a novel P fertilizer for weed management and pathogen control. *Plant Biotechnol. J.* 15:1493-1508.
- Arve R (1960). Preliminary report on attracting fish by oyster shell plantings in Chincoteague Bay, MD. *Chesap Sci* 1: 58–65.
- Castel J Labourg PJ Escaravage V Auby I Garcia ME (1989). Influence of seagrass beds and oyster parks on the abundance and biomass patterns of meio and macrobenthos in tidal flats. *Estuar Coast Shelf Sci* 28: 71–85.
- Cerco CF Noel MR (2010). Monitoring, modelling, and management impacts of bivalve filter feeders in the oligohaline and tidal fresh regions of the Chesapeake Bay system. *Ecol. Modell.*, 22: 1054–1064.
- Cerrato R Lonsdale DJ Caron DA Schaffner A (2004). Effect of the northern quahog *Mercenaria mercenaria* on the development of blooms of the brown tide alga *Aureococcus anophagefferens*. *Mar. Ecol. Prog. Ser.*, 281: 93–108.
- Cloern JE (1982). Does the benthos control phytoplankton biomass in south San Francisco Bay? *Mar. Ecol. Prog. Ser.*, 9: 191–202.
- Commito JA Como S Grupe BM Dowa WE (2008). Species diversity in the softbottom intertidal zone: biogenic structure, sediment, and macrofauna across mussel bed spatial scales. *J Exp Mar Biol Ecol* 366: 70–81.
- Cordell D Drangert J-O White S (2009). The story of phosphorus: Global food security and food for thought. *Global Environmental Change*, 19: 292-305.
- Delago DF (2021). Investigating larval spillover from oyster aquaculture through geospatial Habitat Suitability Index modeling: A Damariscotta River estuary case study. Graduate Program in Ocean Foods Systems, University of New England, Maine, USA.
- Dittmann S (1990). Mussel beds — amensalism or amelioration for intertidal fauna? *Helgol Meeresunters* 44: 335–352.
- Ehrlich MK Harris LA (2015). A review of existing eastern oyster filtration rate models. *Ecological Modelling*, 297(), 201–212.
- Ford H (2011). The effects of shellfish aquaculture on chlorophyll-a in the North East Pacific Ocean. School of Environmental Studies, University of Victoria. Pp 78.
- Foster-Smith, RL (1975). The effect of concentration of suspension on the filtration rates and pseudofaecal production for *Mytilus edulis* L., *Cerastoderma edule* (L.) and *Venerupis pullastra* (Montagu). *Journal of Experimental Marine Biology and Ecology*, v. 17, p. 1-22.
- Gentry RR et al. (2020). Exploring the potential for marine aquaculture to contribute to ecosystem services. *Reviews in Aquaculture*, 12: 499–512.
- Gifford S, Dunstan RH, O’connor W, Roberts T, Toia R (2004). Pearl aquaculture-profitable environmental remediation? *Science of Total Environment*, v. 319, n. 1–3, p. 27–37.
- Higgins C, Stephenson K, Brown B (2011). Nutrient bioassimilation capacity of aquacultured oysters: quantification of an ecosystem service. *Journal of Environmental Quality*, v. 40, n. 1, p. 271–277.
- Jones AB, Preston NP (1999). Sydney rock oyster, *Saccostrea commercialis* (Iredale & Roughley), filtration of shrimp farm effluent: the effects on water quality. *Aquaculture Research*, v. 30, n. 1, p. 51–57.
- Jones CG, Lawton JH, Shachak M (1994). Organisms as ecosystem engineers. *Oikos* 69: 373–386.
- Kochmann J Buschbaum C Volkenborn N Reise K (2008). Shift from native mussels to alien oysters: differential effects of ecosystem engineers. *Journal of Experimental Marine Biology and Ecology*, 364 (1), 1-10.
- Lenihan HS (1999). Physical-biological coupling on oyster reefs: how habitat structure influences individual performance. *Ecol Monogr* 69: 251–275.
- Markert A Wehrmann A Kroencke I (2010). Recently established *Crassostrea*-reefs versus native *Mytilus*-beds: differences in ecosystem engineering affects the macrofaunal communities (Wadden Sea of Lower Saxony, southern German Bight). *Biological Invasions*, 12: 15–32.
- Nelson KA, Leonard LA, Posey MH, Alphin TD, Mallin MA (2004). Using transplanted oyster (*Crassostrea virginica*) beds to improve water quality in small tidal creeks: a pilot study. *Journal of Experimental Marine Biology and Ecology*, n. 298, p. 347-368.
- Newell RIE (1988). Ecological changes in Chesapeake Bay: Are they the result of overharvesting the eastern oyster (*Crassostrea virginica*)? In: Lynch MP, Krome EC (eds) *Understanding the estuary. Advances in Chesapeake Bay research*, Chesapeake Research Consortium Publ 129, Gloucester Point, VA, p 536–546.
- Newell RIE (2004). Ecosystem influences of natural and cultivated populations of suspension-feeding bivalve molluscs: a review. *Journal of Shellfish Research*, 23: 51-61.

- Newell RIE, Fisher TR, Holyoke RR, Cornwell JC (2005). Influence of eastern oysters on nitrogen and phosphorus regeneration in Chesapeake Bay, USA. In: Dame R Olenin S (eds). The comparative roles of suspension feeders in ecosystems. Springer, Dordrecht, the Netherlands.
- O'Connor W, Gifford SP (2008). Environmental impacts of pearl farming. In: Southgate PC, Lucas JS (eds) The pearl oyster. Elsevier Press, Oxford, pp 497–525.
- Ozbay et al. (2017). Eastern oyster (*Crassostrea virginica*) aquaculture and diversity of associated species. Delaware State University, Department of Agriculture and Natural Resources, USA, pp 55.
- Sinha R Thomas J-BE Strand Å Söderqvist T Stadmark J Franzen F Ingmansson I Gröndahl F Hasselström L (2022). Quantifying nutrient recovery by element flow analysis: Harvest and use of seven marine biomasses to close N and P loops. Resources, Conservation and Recycling, 178, 106031.
- Songsangjinda P, Matsuda O, Yamamoto T, Rajendran N, Maeda H (2000). The role of suspended oyster culture on nitrogen cycle in Hiroshima Bay. Journal of Oceanography, v.56, n. 2, p. 223–231.
- Sousa R Gutiérrez JL Aldridge DC (2009). Non-indigenous invasive bivalves as ecosystem engineers. Biol. Inv., 11: 2367–2385.
- Sverdrup et al. (2013). Peak metals, minerals, energy, wealth, food and population; urgent policy considerations for a sustainable society. J. Earth Sci. Eng. (2013), pp. 499-534.
- The Nature Conservancy (2021). Global Principles of Restorative Aquaculture. Arlington, VA. Pp 81.
- Theuerkauf et al. (2019). A global spatial analysis reveals where marine aquaculture can benefit nature and people. PLoS ONE 14(10): e0222282.
- Theuerkauf et al. (2021). Habitat value of bivalve shellfish and seaweed aquaculture for fish and invertebrates: Pathways, synthesis and next steps. Reviews in Aquaculture, 00:1–19.
- Thomas J-B E Sinha R Strand Å et al. (2021). Marine biomass for a circular blue-green bioeconomy? A life cycle perspective on closing nitrogen and phosphorus land–marine loops. J Ind Ecol. 2021; 1– 18.
- Wall CC Peterson BJ Gobler CJ (2008). Facilitation of seagrass *Zostera marina* productivity by suspension-feeding bivalves. MEPS, 357: 165-174.
- Ysebaert T, Walles B, Haner J, Hancock B (2019). Habitat Modification and Coastal Protection by Ecosystem-Engineering Reef-Building Bivalves. In: Smaal AC, Ferreira JG, Grant J, Petersen J K, Strand Ø (eds.). Goods and Services of Marine Bivalves. Springer.
- zu Ermgassen P, Gamble C, Debney A, Colsoul B, Fabra M, Sanderson WG, Strand Å, Preston J, (eds) (2020). European Native Oyster Habitat Restoration Handbook. The Zoological Society of London, UK., London, UK. Pp. 31.